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Digital Media and Its Role in Cultural Diplomacy

Media Digital dan Peranannya dalam Diplomasi Budaya

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Abstract

In the current era of digital globalization, the role of digital media in cultural diplomacy is becoming increasingly important. Digital media has changed the way countries interact and share their culture with the world. Through platforms such as the internet, social media and other digital content, cultural diplomacy becomes more accessible and spreads more quickly. However, along with the benefits, new challenges arise such as privacy, information security and content management. This review examines the role of digital media in cultural diplomacy, analyzes its impact, and identifies challenges and opportunities. This research aims to optimize digital media to strengthen intercultural relations and encourage intercultural understanding in the digital era by exploring effective strategies for using digital media for cultural diplomacy purposes.

Keywords: Digital Media, Cultural Diplomacy

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INTRODUCTION

Digital media significantly influences cultural diplomacy practices in the contemporary era. The Fourth Industrial Revolution has seen a surge in the use of digital media for diplomatic services, particularly during the COVID-19 pandemic (Zulkarnain & Suharyono, 2022). Digital diplomacy, operating through social networks, has become an essential tool for influencing global events and communities, shaping communication norms, and enhancing a country's international appeal (Makananise & Sundani, 2023). This transformation reshapes artistic communication media, empowers new actors, and equips them with tools to enhance global communication campaigns, as evidenced by the recalibration of cultural diplomacy practices with new media technologies and data practices (Reshetnikova & Samokhina, 2023). Media diplomacy, exemplified by Al Jazeera, has demonstrated the positive impact of digital media in implementing diplomatic strategies and enhancing soft power on a global scale (Grincheva, 2022).

Digital media plays a crucial role in facilitating cultural exchange between countries, serving as a powerful tool for cultural communication and diplomacy. It enables the dissemination of cultural initiatives, shapes public perception, and influences social and cultural behavior models (Ivashchenko, 2022). Through digital platforms, traditional cultures can be promoted internationally, fostering a new image of a country and bridging cultural gaps (Yi, 2023). Media is vital in shaping public perception and behavior, making it an essential tool for digital diplomacy and cultural initiatives (Поплавський, 2020). Overall, digital media acts as a catalyst for cultural exchange, promoting understanding and collaboration on a global scale.

Digital media plays a significant role in strengthening bilateral relations between countries through cultural diplomacy. It serves as an effective tool for promoting cultural initiatives, influencing public perception, and facilitating global communication (Поплавський, 2020). New media, such as official Twitter accounts, are used by government organizations to bridge gaps, dispel misunderstandings, and enhance relationships through cultural diplomacy (Tolkun Bekturgan kyzy & Ayhan, 2022). The ongoing digitalization of culture, accelerated by the pandemic, has led to the use of various digital tools in cultural diplomacy efforts, such as virtual tours, online lectures, and

educational events (“Digital Turn’ in Italy’s Cultural Diplomacy,” 2022). Overall, digital media serves as a powerful means for countries to engage in cultural exchange, promote heritage, and foster understanding, ultimately strengthening bilateral relations through cultural diplomacy.

The use of digital media in cultural diplomacy has both positive and negative impacts. Positive effects include the acceleration of digitalization processes in cultural diplomacy during the pandemic, legitimizing digital diplomacy, and enhancing global communication (Reshetnikova & Samokhina, 2023). Digital media also functions as an effective tool for promoting cultural projects, influencing public perception, and fostering cultural diversity through initiatives like the telethon “Songs Unite Us” (Dulayoum, 2023). However, challenges such as inadequate funding, a lack of specialized personnel, and ethical dilemmas regarding software use hinder the full potential of digital cultural diplomacy efforts (Grincheva, 2022).

Digital media significantly impacts the reach and accessibility of cultural diplomacy by providing new avenues for cross-cultural communication and engagement (Elitaş, 2022). Digital media plays a vital role in enhancing intercultural relations and fostering tolerance within cultural diplomacy (Maíz-Arévalo, 2022). Non-state actors, such as the Guggenheim Museum, leverage digital platforms for cultural diplomacy, projecting cosmopolitan messages globally. While traditional cultural diplomacy relies on exchanges and visits, online communication through various platforms has transformed the nature of cultural diplomacy, enabling countries to shape their international image and engage with foreign publics in more complex ways.

Digital media plays a crucial role in cultural diplomacy by facilitating the dissemination of cultural initiatives and enhancing international relations (Elitaş, 2022). Through digital platforms, countries can promote their cultural heritage, engage with global audiences, and effectively influence public perception (Mertoğlu, 2022). The use of social media, internet platforms, and online media outlets allows for the implementation of cultural projects as tools of digital diplomacy, encouraging understanding and cross-cultural cooperation (Reshetnikova & Samokhina, 2023). Additionally, digital technology has transformed traditional diplomacy, making digital diplomacy a primary tool for achieving public diplomacy goals. The digitalization of public diplomacy has expanded the reach of cultural actors, allowing for the integration of diverse cultural perspectives and the promotion of cultural diversity on a global scale.

RESEARCH METHODS

A literature review, often referred to as a review of literature, is the process of investigating and evaluating literature relevant to a specific research topic or question. This involves gathering, reading, and synthesizing written sources, such as books, journals, articles, and conference papers that have been previously published or authored by experts or researchers in the relevant field.

The research methodology regarding “Digital Media and Its Role in Cultural Diplomacy” should encompass various aspects highlighted in the provided context. Scholars emphasize the need to move beyond just social media sites and explore the diverse digital technologies used in public diplomacy activities, such as WhatsApp groups, network analysis, big data analytics, and algorithms (Reshetnikova & Samokhina, 2023). The impact of the COVID-19 pandemic has accelerated the digitalization of cultural diplomacy, leading to the utilization of tools such as virtual museum tours, online concerts, and educational events, despite challenges like funding and ethical considerations (“Digital Turn’ in Italy’s Cultural Diplomacy,” 2022). Geopolitical changes have shifted the discourse of cultural diplomacy towards incorporating culture into climate agendas and sustainable development goals, alongside digitalization efforts (Tabarintseva-Romanova, 2022). Digital communication technologies, particularly social media, play a crucial role in shaping public perception and international agendas, as seen in Turkey’s digital diplomacy efforts (Mertoğlu, 2022). The Fourth Industrial Revolution further underscores the importance of digital media in diplomatic practices, especially during the COVID-19 pandemic, highlighting its role in driving social change in the Global South (Makananise & Sundani, 2023).

DISCUSSION

Digital media plays a crucial role in cultural diplomacy by facilitating intercultural dialogue, broadcasting cultural codes globally, and promoting cultural diversity (Elitaş, 2022). The digitalization of cultural diplomacy has been accelerated by the pandemic, leading to the use of virtual tours, online

lectures, and various cultural events to overcome physical barriers (Grincheva, 2022). This shift to digital platforms has enabled the implementation of innovative cultural projects, such as the telethon "Songs Unite Us," which promotes cultural heritage and fosters global communication (Tabarintseva-Romanova, 2022). Furthermore, the evolving landscape of cultural diplomacy involves exploring new hybrid models and digitally mediated environments for international cultural communication, engaging a variety of actors beyond traditional state-driven relationships. Overall, digital media serves as a powerful tool for enhancing cultural exchange, understanding, and cooperation on a global scale.

CONCLUSION

Digital media has become a significant force in influencing and shaping cultural diplomacy in the contemporary era. With its ability to disseminate information quickly and widely, digital media has facilitated more intensive cultural interactions between countries, making them more accessible to a global audience. The role of digital media in cultural diplomacy includes its use as a tool to promote a country's culture to international audiences, facilitate cultural exchanges, and strengthen intercultural relationships between nations.

Digital media enables countries and cultural organizations to create engaging and relevant content, which can enhance their cultural image in the eyes of the world and expand their cultural influence. Despite its many benefits, the use of digital media in cultural diplomacy also faces several challenges, including issues related to information security, content control, and user privacy.

To fully leverage the potential of digital media in cultural diplomacy, countries need to develop effective strategies that include identifying long-term and short-term goals, producing relevant and engaging content, and regularly monitoring and evaluating their performance. Thus, the conclusion emphasizes that digital media plays a significant role in modern cultural diplomacy and that its use requires a careful and strategic approach to achieve desired outcomes.

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